

1 **PZT-cobalt ferrite particulate composites: densification and lead loss controlled by**
2 **quite-fast sintering**

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22 **Abstract**
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26 **During densification at 1100-1200°C of particulate lead zirconate titanate (PZT)/cobalt ferrite (CF, 26-81**
27 **mol%) composites, side reactions do occur that are detrimental to the properties of the so-obtained**
28 **material. Such reactions are promoted by initial PbO loss, the extent of which can be determined by**
29 **means of XRD analysis of the densified samples taking into account the amount of ZrO₂ and the**
30 **variations of the perovskite's tetragonality. In this process, titania is produced which reacts with CF to**
31 **form cobalt titanate. Microstructural characterization showed that CF grain size distribution can be mono-**
32 **or bi-modal, and CF overgrowth was found to affect the coercivity of the material. In the case of the**
33 **PZT:CF 74:26 composites, full densification and prevention of unwanted side reactions was achieved by**
34 **designing a quite-fast sintering process. The high coercivity (789 Oe) displayed by these composites is**
35 **related to the good dispersion of 250 nm euhedral CF grains in the PZT matrix and limited PZT grain**
36 **growth (240 nm).**
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53 **Keywords:** microstructural analysis; XRD; phase formation; magnetic properties.
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1. Introduction

The increasing interest in advanced materials with coupled ferromagnetic and ferroelectric ferroic orders is motivated by modern technological requirements of multifunctionality, integration and high performance of transducers, actuators, sensors, filters, phase shifters, storage applications and miniaturized antennas [1, 2]. Magnetolectric (ME) composites can be developed in several different combinations by mixing magnetostrictive and piezoelectric materials displaying different connectivity, such as particulate composites [3, 4], laminated composites [5, 6], nanoparticulate thin films [7, 8], nanopillar film structures [9], ultrathin films [10]. Particulate ceramic composites have the advantages of low cost, simple production technology, good ME effect and easy control of electrical and magnetic properties when the ferroelectric phase (generally a perovskite) and the ferromagnetic phase (a ferrite with spinel structure) are mixed in a favourable proportion under the percolation threshold of the ferromagnetic phase, characterized by a lower dielectric constant [11-13]. The macroscopic ME properties are affected by the degree of magnetic phase dispersion and distribution, and also by the final density which, for a particulate composite with a given dispersion and distribution, is proportional to the solid/solid interface density. Therefore, achieving full density extent is of paramount importance as the fact that the quasi-intrinsic ME effects are originated from the interfacial strain-mediated coupling of piezoelectricity and magnetostriction [14]. The bonding between magnetic and ferroelectric particles must be strengthened and the influence of low resistance ferromagnetic phase on the polarization of the ferroelectric one must be decreased as well. This can be achieved by producing fully densified microstructure where an as high as possible amount of ferromagnetic phase (below the percolation threshold) is dispersed and homogeneously distributed in the ferroelectric matrix. A great research effort is in progress to improve the fabrication of PZT–CoFe₂O₄ (PZT–CF) composites due to the excellent piezoelectric properties showed by the PZT material and the large magnetostrictive coefficient of CF [15-17]. Many papers reported the ME properties of said composites and claim that PZT and CF do not react during the sintering process, while less attention is given to the densification and the effects of the porosity on the ME coupling [16, 17, 18]. Sentences like: “densely sintered” are often reported with no

1 actual density values being mentioned. Recently, 97% relative density was achieved by microwave-
2 sintering of PZT/CF (80/20) composites produced by a novel sol-gel route [4]. A further issue is the lead
3 volatilization that occurs during the sintering process, which causes residual porosity to be present in the
4 material and decreases the piezoelectric response of the composite. Atkin and Fulrath [19] found that in
5 the multiphase system the PbO activity, defined as the ratio of PbO partial pressure above the lead-
6 compound (PZT), must be constant at a value between zero and one. Thus, when PZT and CF particles
7 are pressed together, if reactions occur able to produce zirconium and/or titanium oxides, the PZT
8 particles can lose PbO to maintain the PbO activity constant [19, 20]. In this work PZT-CF particulate
9 composites with increasing CF content, from 26 to 81 mol%, were produced, and the focus was placed on
10 densification process issues like PbO losses and reactivity of the CF particles with titanium oxide. The
11 densification parameters were optimized in order to achieve full densification and control of the
12 microstructure, and to reduce mechanical defects and interphase diffusion, using a conventional, but
13 optimized, ceramic process. An easy method to calculate the PbO loss was proposed by quantifying the
14 lead-deficient phases through X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD) analysis.

31 **2. Experimental**

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33 (1-x)Pb_{0.988}(Zr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48})_{0.976}Nb_{0.024}O₃-(x)CoFe₂O₄ (PZTN-CF) composites were produced by a two-step
34 solid-state-reaction method. Perovskite PZTN powders were prepared by the mixed oxides route, calcined
35 at 800 °C and milled down to 0.7 μm [21]. Spinel CF powders were prepared by the mixed oxides route,
36 calcined at 1000 °C and milled down to 0.2 μm [22]. The composites were prepared by mixing the as-
37 synthesized powders according to the (1-x)PZTN-xCF molar compositional scheme, with x = 0.26, 0.32,
38 0.58, and 0.81, which were labelled as PZTN-CF26, PZTN-CF32, PZTN-CF58, and PZTN-CF81,
39 respectively. The powder mixtures were wet ball-milled, dried and subjected to cold linear pressing at 50
40 MPa to produce 10 mm diam., 2÷3 mm thick disks. Isostatic pressing at 250 MPa was applied to the disks
41 to obtain green homogeneous PZTN-CF bodies. The sintering treatments were performed in lead-
42 saturated atmosphere setting soaking temperature and time at 1200 °C for 2 h, 1150 °C for 2 h and 1100
43 °C for 0.5 h. A constant heating rate of 6 °C/min was employed to reach the sintering temperature
44 plateau, and the sintered samples were brought back to room temperature by natural cooling of the
45 furnace.

1 The crystalline phases were identified by XRPD using a Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer (θ - θ)
2 with Cu K α . The samples were scanned in $15^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 80^\circ$ range of at 2.4 $^\circ$ /min scanning rate. The
3 quantitative determination of the phases was performed with the commercial BRUKER EVA program,
4 obtaining a weighted residual value R_{wp} between 3.5 and 7.7.
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9 The microstructure of the sintered samples was investigated by SEM analysis of cross-sections performed
10 on a ZEISS SIGMA Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) system. The relative
11 density of the sintered samples was calculated from the density determined by the Archimedes' method
12 normalizing to the theoretical density obtained as the average of PZTN and CF theoretical densities
13 (8.006 g cm $^{-3}$ and 5.304 g cm $^{-3}$, respectively). Magnetic hysteresis loops were measured at room
14 temperature at magnetic field strengths in the range of (0-10kOe) on a vibrating sample magnetometer
15 (MicroMagTM VSM model 3900 from Princeton Measurements Co.).
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25 **3. Results and discussion**

26 *3.1 Phase analysis and microstructure*

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28 Fig.1 shows the XRPD patterns of the sintered samples. All the diffraction peaks for the compositions
29 sintered at 1100 $^\circ$ C for 0.5 h were indexed to the cubic spinel structure of CoFe $_2$ O $_4$ (PDF No 22-1086, for
30 the sake of clarity, only the strongest I_{CF} (3 1 1) peak was marked with a rhombus), and to the tetragonal
31 perovskite structure of PZTN (PDF No 70-4060, I_{PZTN} (1 0 1), circle). As was expected, the intensity of
32 the CoFe $_2$ O $_4$ diffraction peaks increases vs. increasing CoFe $_2$ O $_4$ content, while the intensity of PZTN the
33 peak decreases. Upon temperature increase to 1150 $^\circ$ C and 1200 $^\circ$ C, XRPD shows that the starting Zr/Ti
34 ratio ($\tau = \text{Zr/Ti}$) is not kept constant in the perovskite phase, as pointed out by the split of the (0 0 2) and
35 (2 0 0) diffraction peaks (at $2\theta \approx 44^\circ$ and 45° , respectively). In fact, according to the crystal geometry
36 equations, which correlate the d-spacings with the Miller indices, for the tetragonal symmetry the d-
37 spacing of the (0 0 2) diffraction peak is directly proportional to the c lattice parameter ($2d_{(002)} = c$)
38 while the d-spacing of the (2 0 0) diffraction peak is directly proportional to the a lattice parameter ($2d_{(200)}$
39 $= a$). In particular, this is most clearly seen in the sample with the highest PZTN amount (see
40 magnified view on the right of Fig.1, covering the 43.5° to 46° 2θ region) but this is also true for all the
41 other samples. The (0 0 2) diffraction peak widens towards smaller 2θ degrees with increasing sintering
42 temperature, whereas the a -axis dimension is not as strongly affected. This feature reveals that the crystal
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1 tetragonality, c/a , of the PZTN phase increases vs. increasing sintering temperature, owing to the
2 formation of perovskite phases with lower Zr/Ti ratio. Moreover, peaks belonging to the undesired phases
3 of baddeleyite, ZrO_2 (PDF No 65-1022, I_{ZrO_2} (1 1 1), square) and $CoTiO_3$ (PDF No 65-1022, I_{CoTiO_3} (0 1
4 2), cross) were also identified in the sample sintered for 2 h at 1200 °C and 1150 °C. These results are
5 reliable as their magnitude is well above the detection limit of the equipment. Other phases possibly
6 present in the sample (such as Fe_2O_3 , Nb_2O_5 , $FeNbO_4$, etc...) were not detected, maybe because their
7 XRPD features were hidden by those of the main phases. The presence of the baddeleyite phase justifies
8 the stoichiometry change of the PZTN phase, depending on the sintering temperature. This suggests that
9 PbO depletion occurred during heat treatment at temperature higher than 1100°C. The relative intensity of
10 the highest ZrO_2 peak, normalized to the starting PZTN amount, increases with the increasing of the
11 sintering temperature, which confirms that ZrO_2 forms due to PbO volatilization. Lead evaporation is not
12 a consequence of cobalt titanate formation or other reactions between PZTN and CF particles, because the
13 extent of these reactions should be directly correlated with the $CoFe_2O_4$ content in the composites. On the
14 other hand, cobalt titanate formation may promote PbO volatilization to the following reactions:

42 where f is a molar fraction representing the amount of PbO losses; y and z are the molar fractions that
43 define the Zr/Ti molar ratio in the produced PZTN perovskite phases. The amount f of PbO loss can be
44 calculated from the Zr/Ti ratio variation ($\tau = 0.52y/(0.48z) = 0.52y/(1-0.52y)$) if the amount of one of the
45 products is known. As regards to the Zr/Ti ratio variation, the (0 0 2) diffraction peak's broadening at
46 smaller 2θ values is the result of a convolution of several diffraction peaks each of them reflecting the
47 presence of a specific amount of perovskite phase characterised by a specific lattice elongation along the
48 tetragonal c -axis, as defined by the Zr/Ti ratio. In the present study, no attempt was made to quantify the
49 amount of each perovskite stoichiometry that could be present in the sample. It was assumed that, besides
50 the starting perovskite phase, characterized by a Zr/Ti ratio of 52/48, there was only another one with a

Zr/Ti ratio of 52y/48z – chosen so that the weighted residual value R_{wp} was minimized. It is convenient to choose baddeleyite (ZrO_2) formation as the reference process rather than that of other products since, as it can be seen from the XRPD evidence, the relative intensities of the detected ZrO_2 peaks are higher than that of the $CoTiO_3$ phase, and of the tetragonal phases with lower Zr/Ti molar ratio. Even though the $CoTiO_3$ diffractions peaks are very weak and, for some samples, are hidden by experimental noise, its formation is expected because the $TiO_2/CoFe_2O_4$ molar ratio should be lower than 1 [23]. Niobium oxide's stoichiometric coefficient (0.012·f) is one order of magnitude smaller than that of the other phases, and it goes thus undetected by the XRPD analysis and thus its amount was considered constant in the PZTN. Once the baddeleyite molar fraction (b) and the change of the amount of Zr in the produced perovskite (y) has been quantified by quantitative XRPD analysis, the PbO loss δ , expressed as molar fraction, was calculated through the following equation:

$$\delta = m_{Pb}(b/m_{Zr} - 1 + y)/y \quad (3)$$

where m_{Pb} and m_{Zr} are the stoichiometric coefficients of lead and zirconium in the starting perovskite phase, respectively. In our case, $m_{Pb} = 0.988$ and $m_{Zr} = 0.52 * 0.976 = 0.50752$.

Results, reported in Fig.2, show an increase of PbO loss vs. increasing sintering temperature (Fig.2, dashed lines). The extent of PbO loss is between 0.2% and 3.5%, 8.3% and 11.7%, and 25.7% and 27.7% for the samples sintered at 1100°C, 1150°C and 1200°C, respectively. The δ values trend is confirmed by the density trend (Fig. 2, solid lines) which is sort of a mirror image of the previous. An inverse correlation between the densification and the PbO loss is seen in Fig.2. At a given sintering temperature, the maximum δ values, which correspond to the minimum percent ρ values, are seen in the PZTN-CF58 samples. These results can be explained considering that the extent of lead loss (and thus that of porosity formation) is proportional on one hand to the amount of PZTN (which is the source of PbO) and on the other hand is correlated to the molar fraction x of CF, which reacts with TiO_2 . It is therefore reasonable that the $\rho_{\%}$ and δ curves display a minimum or maximum, respectively, on the x axis, with the highest relative density value (about 99%) corresponding to the lowest PbO loss (0.2%). The relative density is less precise when the amount of the reactions' products (described above) is higher that makes the theoretical density less precisely known. This means that the $\rho_{\%}$ values are more precise when the δ

1 values are low, while the δ values are more precise when their values are high. However all the detected
2 secondary phases have a density lower than that of PZTN, so when some reactions occur the calculated
3 relative density is always underestimated.
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7 The results on PbO losses and densities are in agreement with the SEM analysis evidences shown in
8 Fig.3, in particular as regards to porosity. In the first column of Fig.3 ((a), (c) and (e)), the whole series of
9 PZTN-CF58 microstructures is shown as an example, since such composition is characterized by the
10 lowest densities for all the investigated sintering conditions. It can be seen that the amount and size of the
11 pores decrease vs. decreasing sintering temperature, large spherical pores being present only in the
12 samples sintered at 1150 °C and 1200 °C (Fig.3 (a)-(d)). From the backscattered images, it can be seen
13 that the fully dense PZTN-CF26_1100 sample (Fig. 3 (f)) displays spinel CF crystals (dark grains) well
14 mixed and uniformly distributed in the perovskite PZTN matrix (bright grains). The other samples
15 sintered at 1100 °C for 0.5 h display higher amount of CF aggregates and porosity, as can be seen in Fig.3
16 (e). Backscattered images confirm the above discussed reactions as can be seen from the reaction
17 products (indicated by black arrows in Fig.3). Such reactions brought about severe volume reduction
18 when PbO losses occurred. Considering the calculated PbO molar fraction losses (f), the theoretical
19 volume contraction is in the [0%, 1%], [2%, 3%], [6%, 7%] ranges for the samples sintered at 1100 °C,
20 1150 °C, and 1200 °C, respectively. Moreover, if it is taken into account that locally f can be considered
21 unity (i.e. full PbO depletion), the local volume contraction reaches 25%. This explains the cracks that
22 appear near to the reaction products (Fig. 3 (d), magnified in Fig. 3 (a) and 3 (c)). The increase of
23 tetragonality - which is inversely proportional to τ - is negligible. In fact, theoretical consideration
24 indicate that the maximum volume expansion of 0.9% should occur when $\tau = 0$ and $f = 0.52$ (this is the
25 lower bound for PbO loss if $\tau = 0$). From SEM analysis, a third aspect to be highlighted is the different
26 microstructure evolution in terms of grain size distribution and grain morphology. It can be seen that at
27 1100 °C CF grains show octahedral crystal habit, and are characterized by a grain size smaller than 1 μm .
28 In particular, the fully densified PZTN-CF26_1100 sample shows euhedral CF crystals (zoom of Fig.3
29 (f)), while in the other samples sintered at 1100 °C for 0.5 h CF grains are characterized by subhedral
30 crystals as a consequence of crowded growth promoted by the higher CF amount. Increasing the sintering
31 temperature at 1150 °C causes the grain size of faceted CF grains to increase and overgrown CF grains
32 appear. This can be seen in Fig.3 (b), (c), and (d), where the faces of the larger grains, indicated by white
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1 arrows, are marked by outcropping parallel striae. This kind of growth, in agreement with the spinel law,
2 takes place by multiple parallel twinning along the $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions and produces twin lamellae of
3 about 200 nm [22]. At 1200 °C the sizes of euhedral and subhedral grains display a further increase. The
4 quantitative grain size distributions are shown in Fig.4. It can be seen that the CF grain distributions
5 (Fig.4 (b-e)) depend on sample composition (CF content) as well as on the sintering conditions (the grain
6 size increases vs. increasing sintering temperature for all samples). Looking at the CF grain distributions
7 of the sample sintered at 1100 °C for 0.5 h (solid lines), the narrow sub-micrometric distributions show a
8 mode value that decreases at the CF content decreases. At 1150 °C for 2 h (dashed lines) a slightly
9 bimodal distribution appears: the mode value of the main peak shows opposite trend, i.e. it increases vs.
10 decreasing CF content, but the fraction of larger grains, i.e. overgrown grains in the range of 12-18 μm ,
11 increases vs. increasing of CF content. PZTN grain growth is proportional to the sintering temperature
12 and does not depend strongly on the composition (Fig.4 (a)). The mean size of the PZTN grains, in the
13 samples densified by conventional sintering, are similar to those of pure PZTN samples sintered at the
14 same temperatures [24]. Quite-fast sintering leads to a substantial reduction in the mean grain size from 1
15 μm (expected value by conventional sintering) to 0.24 μm . It is well known that, in niobium-doped PZT
16 system, grain refinement below to 0.8 μm marks the beginning of a drastic reduction of piezoelectric and
17 dielectric properties [24]. This reduction of the electromechanical coupling can be due to lattice
18 distortion, which reduces the c/a tetragonality [24]. In that case, the contribution of the decrease of grain
19 size translates into an increase of the value of γ that should be accounted for to allow a more precise
20 determination of PbO loss (δ), avoiding its underestimation. Another critical issue related to fine PZT
21 grains, in particulate ME composites, arises from the electric contribution of boundaries of ferroelectric
22 grains, which increases as the grain size decreases [25]. Consequently, the properties of ME composites
23 characterized by a fine-grained PZT matrix are expected to strongly depend on the electric boundary
24 conditions of the ferroelectric phase. In particular, the presence of low permittivity and nonferroelectric
25 boundary layers [25] can make more difficult or outright the electrical poling of ME particulate
26 composites. In fact, even if the percolation of ferromagnetic phase did not occur, the electric permittivity,
27 determined by the combination of intrinsic size effects of the ferroelectric phase, “dilution” effect due to
28 the nonferroelectric grain boundaries, ferromagnetic phase, and porosity, cannot be appropriated for
29 reaching the saturation polarization of the ferroelectric phase in particulate ME composites.

1 These results highlight the advantages and disadvantages of the quite-fast sintering process for the
2 production of ME particulate composites. The quite-high heating rate may have triggered the contribution
3 of the high energy stored in the milled particles in enhancing the sintering, thus reducing the energy
4 released by means of the other processes before the densification, while limiting the PbO losses that occur
5 at temperatures higher than 900 °C if the vapour-phase PbO is not kept at its equilibrium value. In order
6 words, through quite-fast sintering it is possible i) to obtain at a lower temperature the good sinterability
7 of milled powders [26] conventionally achieved at higher temperatures, ii) reduce PbO losses, iii) avoid
8 CF overgrowth, and, iv) to fully densify the PZTN/CF particulate composite. All these features are
9 prerequisites to obtain good ME coupling, but, on the other hand, the smaller PZT grain size ($< 0.8 \mu\text{m}$)
10 achieved after sintering affects the piezoelectric properties and thus it will be at the expenses of the ME
11 properties. Anyway, above results are highly innovative and confirm that it is possible to produce a fully
12 dense PZTN/CF particulate composite by proper design of the conventional ceramic process, in order to
13 control PbO losses and the formation of undesirable phases at the PZTN/CF interface during sintering. In
14 our opinion, there are three main points that should be addressed in order to further improve the process.
15 The first one is the milling treatment which can be significantly strengthened by using, for example,
16 planetary milling in order to increase the powders sinterability and allow an enhanced PZTN grain growth
17 [26]. The second point regards the quite-fast sintering; in particular, it might be convenient to increase the
18 heating rate further while decreasing the soaking time in order to exploit its advantages. The third point is
19 the annealing step, which should be designed to increase the size of PZT grains obtained after the
20 sintering. The annealing temperature and time should be chosen in order to allow grain growth of the
21 ferroelectric phase, possibly above $2 \mu\text{m}$, avoiding the development of core-shell microstructures caused
22 by PbO evaporation [27].

23 *3.2 Magnetic properties*

24 The magnetic hysteresis loops for the samples are presented in Fig. 4; they indicate that all the composites
25 have ferromagnetic properties due to the presence of the CF phase. It has been experimentally confirmed
26 that ferromagnetic materials follow the law of approach to saturation, which describes the dependence of
27 magnetization on the applied field for $H > H_c$ [28]. Using the equation $M = M_s [1 - 8/105 (K_1 / (M_s H))^2] + \kappa H$,
28 which describes the magnetization near M_s for random polycrystalline specimens with cubic anisotropy,
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1 M_s was estimated through a nonlinear fitting [29] solved by Levenberg Marquardt interaction algorithm
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3 (the damped least-squares method used to solve non-linear least squares problems). In the above equation
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5 K_1 is the first order cubic anisotropy constant, κ is the high-field susceptibility, and κH is the forced
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7 magnetization, also called the paramagnetism-like term, caused by an increase in the spontaneous
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9 magnetization itself especially at high field. The saturation magnetization, M_s , and remnant
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11 magnetization, M_r , of the composites reported in Table 1, increase almost linearly with the increase of CF
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13 content, as should be expected. Owing to forced magnetization, the estimated saturation magnetization M_s
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15 is affected by the contributions of all phases present in the samples with a magnetic susceptibility
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17 different from zero at the investigated frequencies; the remnant magnetization M_r is mainly due to the
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19 ferromagnetic phases (all phases with a permanent magnetization at zero field), that, in our case, is only
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21 the CF. The M_r values are in agreement with the above discussed reactions that occur in the samples
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23 depending on the sintering temperature. In fact, when the PbO losses are limited, the M_r values increase
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25 due to the reduced formation of CoTiO_3 , as the latter lowers the amount of CF. It is important to highlight
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27 that the M_s values match well the theoretical one, and both M_s and M_r are higher than the values reported
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29 in the literature for similar composites, suggesting that some reaction could have occurred in the materials
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31 studied in this work [20]. The measured H_c values within the range reported in the literature for bulk
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33 cobalt ferrite [30, 31], and their trend follows the inverse proportionality correlation to the grain size of
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35 CF, d_{CF} , (Fig. 6), as is expected from the theory ($H_c \propto 1/d_{\text{CF}}$) [32]. This evidence suggests a multidomain
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37 or pseudo-single domain magnetic behaviour – small multidomain grains characterized by a mixture of
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39 single domain-like (high remanence) and multidomain-like (low coercivity) [33] –CF grains. In fact, it is
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41 known that coercivity of CF increases with decreasing particle size (multidomain range), gets to a
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43 maximum when the grain size is 28 nm [34], and then decreases to zero (single domain range) [35] when
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45 superparamagnetism appears for extremely small nanoparticles (superparamagnetic range). For larger
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47 grain size (> 28 nm), coercivity decreases as the grain subdivides into domains. The slight increase of H_c
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49 for the higher values of d_{CF} (sample sintered at 1200 °C) (Fig. 6) could not invalidate the trend of inverse
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51 proportionality between H_c and d_{CF} , since that should be due to the increase of overgrown CF grain
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53 population which is characterized by high density of stacking faults along the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction (Fig. 4).
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55 In fact it was recently observed that multiparallel-twinned grains display lower susceptibility, and thus an
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57 enhanced hard magnetic behaviour [22]. H_c is also influenced by magneto-crystalline anisotropy [36],
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1 surface anisotropy [37], and anisotropy field at the PZTN-CF interfaces which can induce a pinning of
2 magnetization at the grain boundaries [38]. It is difficult to explain this contribution since the magnetic
3 properties depend on a number of intrinsic and extrinsic effects; these include grain size, differences in
4 particles morphology, crystal defects, distribution of the different cations among (A) and [B] sites, and
5 depend on the processing parameters (mostly the amount of PZTN in the mixture and time and sintering
6 temperature, in the present case) [22, 37-41]. Therefore the relationship with H_c is quite complex. In
7 terms of macroscopic behaviour, the samples sintered at 1100 °C show hard magnetic behaviour with a
8 coercivity of 413 – 789 Oe and a remnant/saturation magnetization ratio of 0.244 – 0.382. These values
9 are comparable with pure nanocrystalline cobalt ferrite characterized by a partially inverted spinel
10 structure [41]. In particular the samples PZTN-CF81_1100 and PZTN-CF26_1100 show H_c and M_r/M_s
11 magnetic parameters comparable with nanocrystalline cobalt ferrite characterized by crystallite size of 35
12 nm and 53 nm, and a degree of inversion of 0.80 and 0.82, respectively [41] (a spinel is totally inverted
13 when the degree of inversion is one). The above crystallite sizes are included in the multidomain field
14 [33] and the M_r/M_s ratios suggest a pseudo-single domain magnetic behaviour [42]. The higher degree of
15 inversion reached by the PZTN-CF26_1100 sample could be attributed to the higher intrinsic strain in the
16 smaller CF grains (as discussed above, see the Fig. 3, the grain size of CF increases with increasing CF
17 content and sintering temperature), which leads to higher shifting of Co^{2+} cations from tetrahedral to
18 octahedral sites [33]. The hard magnetic behaviour due to the higher intrinsic strain, and the full
19 densification support the view that a high value of the ME coefficient, α^{33}_E should be expected.
20 In fact it is found in the literature [4] that for a similar composition α^{33}_E increases from 0.73 mV cm⁻¹ Oe⁻¹
21 to 1.56 mV cm⁻¹ Oe⁻¹ upon increase of the relative density from 92% to 97%. Since an almost fully dense
22 material was produced, the α^{33}_E coefficient at room temperature should be higher than 1.56 mV cm⁻¹ Oe⁻¹
23 due to better mechanical coupling.
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50 4. Conclusions

51 Particulate ceramic composites of the composition $(1-x)Pb_{0.988}(Zr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48})_{0.976}Nb_{0.024}O_3-(x)CoFe_2O_4$
52 (PZTN-CF) were prepared by a solid state reaction method. The XRPD results revealed that consistent
53 PbO losses occur when the sintering temperature is higher than 1100°C. PbO volatilization leaves
54 undesired phases which can react with CF, further increasing PbO losses. An equation to calculate the
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1 molar fraction of PbO loss was proposed taking in to account the amount of baddeleyite formation and the
2 increase of perovskite's tetragonality. An inverse correlation between densification and PbO losses was
3 observed. Uniform microstructures - in terms of phase mixing and grain size growth – were obtained in
4 all studied composites. Almost fully dense ceramics (density 99 %) were obtained by sintering PZTN-CF
5 composites with the 74:26 molar ratio at 1100 °C for 0.5 h by setting a quite-fast heating rate (6 °C/min).
6
7 The latter sample displays very hard magnetic behaviour, with a coercivity of 789 Oe and a saturation
8 magnetization of 14 emu/g (70 emu/g if the ratio of volume magnetization at the saturation on only CF
9 mass is considered). A decrease of the coercive field and remnant magnetization was found at higher
10 sintering temperatures due to the increased reactivity and larger CF grain size. For the samples sintered at
11 1100 °C, the hard magnetic behaviour was found to be proportional to the PZTN amount. This was
12 ascribed to a better dispersion of the small multidomain CF grains in the PZTN matrix and to enhanced
13 pseudo-single domain magnetic behaviour as the CF gran size decreased to 250 nm.
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40 **References**

- 41 [1] C.W. Nan, D.R. Clarke, Effective properties of ferroelectric and/or ferromagnetic composites: a
42 unified approach and its application, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 80 (1997) 1333-1340.
43
44 [2] L. Mitoseriu, V. Buscaglia, M. Viviani, M.T. Buscaglia, I. Pallecchi, C. Harnagea, A. Testino, V.
45 Trefiletti, P. Nanni, A.S. Siri, BaTiO₃–(Ni_{0.5}Zn_{0.5})Fe₂O₄ ceramic composites with ferroelectric and
46 magnetic properties, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 27 (2007) 4379-4382.
47
48 [3] A.R. Iordan, M. Airimioaiei, M. N. Palamaru, C. Galassi, A.V. Sandu, C.E. Ciomaga, F. Prihor, L.
49 Mitoseriu, A. Ianculescu, In situ preparation of CoFe₂O₄–Pb(ZrTi)O₃ multiferroic composites by gel-
50 combustion technique, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 29 (2009) 2807-2813. DOI:
51 10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2009.03.031
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1 [4] C.P. Fernández, F.L. Zabotto, D. Garcia, R.H.G.A. Kiminami, In situ sol-gel co-synthesis under
2 controlled pH and microwave sintering of PZT/CoFe₂O₄ magnetoelectric composite ceramics, *Ceram. Int.*
3 42 (2016) 3239-3249. DOI: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2015.10.115
4
5 [5] J.P. Zhou, H.C. He, Z. Shi, G. Liu, C.W. Nan, Dielectric, magnetic, and magnetoelectric properties of
6 laminated PbZr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48}O₃/CoFe₂O₄ composite ceramics, *J. Appl. Phys.* 100 (2006) 094106-6. DOI:
7 10.1063/1.2358191
8
9 [6] R.C. Pullar, Combinatorial bulk ceramic magnetoelectric composite libraries of strontium hexaferrite
10 and barium titanate, *ACS Comb. Sci.* 14 (2012) 425-433. DOI: 10.1021/co300036m
11
12 [7] J.G. Wan, X.W. Wang, Y.J. Wu, M. Zeng, Y. Wang, H. Jiang, W.Q. Zhou, G.H. Wang, J.H. Liu,
13 Magnetoelectric CoFe₂O₄-Pb(Zr,Ti)O₃ composite thin films derived by a sol-gel process, *Appl. Phys.*
14 *Lett.* 86 (2005) 122501-3. DOI: 10.1063/1.1889237
15
16 [8] S. Ren, M. Wuttig, Magnetoelectric nano-Fe₃O₄/CoFe₂O₄||PbZr_{0.53}Ti_{0.47}O₃ composite, *Appl. Phys.*
17 *Lett.* 92 (2008) 083502. DOI: 10.1063/1.2841064
18
19 [9] S. Ren, R.M. Briber, M. Wuttig, Diblock copolymer based self-assembled nanomagnetoelectric, *Appl.*
20 *Phys. Lett.* 93 (2008)173507-3. DOI: 10.1063/1.3005558
21
22 [10] D. Mukherjee, M. Hordagoda , M.H. Phan, H. Srikanth , S. Witanachchi, P. Mukherjee,
23 Simultaneous enhancements of polarization and magnetization in epitaxial
24 Pb(Zr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48})O₃/La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}MnO₃ multiferroic heterostructures enabled by ultrathin CoFe₂O₄ sandwich
25 layers, *Phys. Rev. B* 91 (2015) 054419-13.
26
27 [11] M.D. Michelena, F. Montero, P. Sánchez, E. López, M.C. Sánchez, C. Aroca, Piezoelectric –
28 magnetostrictive magnetic sensor using stripe actuators, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 242 – 245 (2002) 1160-
29 1162.
30
31 [12] J. Zhai, N. Cai, Z. Shi, Y. Lin, C.W. Nan, Magnetic–dielectric properties of NiFe₂O₄/PZT particulate
32 composites, *J. Phys. D* 37 (2004) 823-827.
33
34 [13] V.M. Petrov, G. Srinivasan, U. Lalestin, M.I. Bichurin, D.S. Tuskov, N. Paddubnaya,
35 Magnetoelectric effects in porous ferromagnetic-piezoelectric bulk composites: experiment and theory,
36 *Phys. Rev. B* 75 (2007) 174422-6.
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1 [14] J.H. Park, M.G. Kim, S.J. Ahn, S. Ryu, H.M. Jang, Interfacial strain-mediated magnetoelectric
2 coupling as reflected in extended X-ray absorption spectra of CoFe_2O_4 -dispersed $\text{Pb}(\text{Zr},\text{Ti})\text{O}_3$ matrix
3 composites, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 321 (2009) 1971–1974. DOI:10.1016/j.jmmm.2008.12.019
4
5 [15] L. Weng, Y. Fu, S. Song, J. Tang, J. Li, Synthesis of lead zirconate titanate–cobalt ferrite
6 magnetoelectric particulate composites via an ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid–citrate gel process, *Scr.*
7 *Mater.* 56 (2007) 465-468.
8
9 [16] A. Gupta, A. Huang, S. Shannigrahi, R. Chatterjee, Improved in Mn and Zn doped CoFe_2O_4 -
10 $\text{PbZr}_{0.52}\text{Ti}_{0.48}\text{O}_3$ particulate composite, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 98 (2011) 112901-3.
11
12 [17] X. Wu, W. Cai, Y. Kan, P. Yang, Y. Liu, H. Bo, X. Lu, J. Zhu, Multiferroic properties of
13 $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{PbZr}_{0.52}\text{Ti}_{0.48}\text{O}_3$ composite ceramics, *Ferroelectrics* 380 (2009) 48-55. DOI:
14 10.1080/00150190902872982
15
16 [18] J.H. Peng, M. Hojamberdiev, H.Q. Li, D.L. Mao, Y.J. Zhao, P. Liu, J.P. Zhou, G.Q. Zhu, Electrical,
17 magnetic, and direct and converse magnetoelectric properties of $(1-x)\text{Pb}(\text{Zr}_{0.52}\text{Ti}_{0.48})\text{O}_3$ - $(x)\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ (PZT-
18 CFO) magnetoelectric composites, *J. Magn. Magn. Mat.* 378 (2015) 298-305.
19
20 [19] R.B. Atkin, R.M. Fulrath, Point defects and sintering of lead zirconate titanate, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*
21 54 (1971) 265-270.
22
23 [20] A.D. James, P.F. Messer, The preparation of transparent PLZT ceramics from oxide powders by
24 liquid sintering, *Trans. J. Br. Ceram. Soc.* 77 (1978) 152-58.
25
26 [21] C.E. Ciomaga, C. Galassi, F. Prihor, I. Dumitru, L. Mitoseriu, A.R. Iordan, M. Airimioaei, M.N.
27 Palamaru, Preparation and properties of the CoFe_2O_4 -Nb-Pb(Zr,Ti) O_3 multiferroic composites prepared
28 in situ by gel-combustion method, *J. All. Comp.* 485 (2009) 372–378. DOI:
29 10.1016/j.jallcom.2009.05.101
30
31 [22] P. Galizia, C. Baldisserrri, C. Capiiani, C. Galassi, Multiple parallel twinning overgrowth in
32 nanostructured dense cobalt ferrite, *Mater. Design* 109 (2016) 19-26. DOI: 10.1016/j.matdes.2016.07.050
33
34 [23] P. Galizia, C. Baldisserrri, C. Galassi, Microstructure development in novel titania–cobalt ferrite
35 ceramic materials, *Ceram. Int.* 42 (2016) 2634-2641. DOI:10.1016/j.ceramint.2015.10.069
36
37 [24] C.A. Randall, N. Kim, J.-P. Kucera, W. Cao, T.R. Shrout, Intrinsic and extrinsic size effects in fine-
38 grained morphotropic-phase-boundary lead zirconate titanate ceramics. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 81 (1998)
39 677-688.
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1 [25] Z. Zhao, V. Buscaglia, M. Viviani, M.T. Buscaglia, L. Mitoseriu, A. Testino, M. Nygren, M.
2
3 Johnsson, P. Nanni, Grain-size effects on the ferroelectric behavior of dense nanocrystalline BaTiO₃
4
5 ceramics. *Phys. Rev. B* 70 (2004) 024107 -8. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevB.70.024107
6
- 7 [26] H. Maiwa, O. Kimura, K. Shoji, H. Ochiai, Low temperature sintering of PZT ceramics without
8
9 additives via an ordinary ceramic route. *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 25 (2005) 2383–2385. DOI:
10
11 10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2005.03.066
12
- 13 [27] E. Breval, M. Klimkiewicz, C. Wang, J.P. Dougherty, Annealing of sintering
14
15 $\text{Pb}_{0.9175}\text{La}_{0.055}\text{Zr}_{0.975}\text{Ti}_{0.025}\text{O}_3$ in air. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 90 (2007) 2664-2666. DOI: 10.1111/j.1551-
16
17 2916.2007.01805.x
18
- 19 [28] R. Becker, W. Döring, *Ferromagnetismus*. Springer, Berlin, 1939. p. 171.
20
- 21 [29] A. Franco, F.C. Silva, High temperature magnetic properties of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles, *Appl.*
22
23 *Phys. Lett.* 96 (2010) 172505-3. DOI: 10.1063/1.3422478
24
- 25 [30] M. Cernea, P. Galizia, I. Ciuchi, G. Aldica, V. Mihalache, L. Diamandescu, C. Galassi, CoFe_2O_4
26
27 magnetic ceramic derived from gel and densified by spark plasma sintering, *J. Alloys. Compd.* 656 (2016)
28
29 854-862.
30
- 31 [31] T. Gaudisson, M. Artus, U. Acevedo, F. Herbst, S. Nowak, R. Valenzuela, S. Ammar, On the
32
33 microstructural and magnetic properties of fine-grained CoFe_2O_4 ceramics produced by combining polyol
34
35 process and spark plasma sintering, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 370 (2014) 87-95.
36
- 37 [32] G.F. Dionne, *Magnetic Oxides*. Springer, 2009. p. 253. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4419-0054-8
38
- 39 [33] R.F. Butler, S.K. Banerjee, Theoretical single-domain grain size range in magnetite and
40
41 titanomagnetite, *J. Geophys. Res.* 80 (1975) 4049–4058. DOI: 10.1029/JB080i029p04049
42
- 43 [34] K. Maaz, A. Mumtaz, S.K. Hasanain, A. Ceylan, Synthesis and magnetic properties of cobalt ferrite
44
45 (CoFe_2O_4) nanoparticles prepared by wet chemical route, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 308 (2007) 289-295.
46
47 DOI: 10.1016/j.jmmm.2006.06.003
48
- 49 [35] S. Sigh, N. Khare, Defects/strain influenced magnetic properties and inverse of surface spin canting
50
51 effect in single domain CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 364 (2016) 783-788. DOI:
52
53 10.1016/j.apsusc.2015.12.205
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1 [36] Y. Melikhov, J.E. Snyder, D.C. Jiles, A.P. Ring, J.A. Paulsen, C.C.H. Lo, K.W. Dennis, Temperature
2 dependence of magnetic anisotropy in Mn-substituted cobalt ferrite, *J. Appl. Phys.* 99 (2006) 08R102.
3
4 DOI: 10.1063/1.2151793
5
6 [37] T. Bala, C.R. Sankar, M. Baidakova, V. Osipov, T. Enoki, P.A. Joy, B.B.L.V. Prasad, M. Sastry,
7
8 Cobalt and magnesium ferrite nanoparticles: preparation using liquid Foams as templates and their
9
10 magnetic characteristics, *Langmuir* 21 (2005) 10638-10643. DOI: 10.1021/la051595k
11
12 [38] R. Pattanayaka, R. Mudulia, R.K. Pandaa, T. Dashb, P. Saha, S. Rauta, S. Panigraha, Investigating
13
14 the effect of multiple grain–grain interfaces on electric and magnetic properties of [50 wt% BaFe₁₂O₁₉–
15
16 50 wt% Na_{0.5}Bi_{0.5}TiO₃] composite system, *Physica B* 485 (2016) 67–77. DOI:
17
18 10.1016/j.physb.2016.01.011
19
20 [39] G.B. Li, S.L. Tang, S.K. Ren, F.M. Zhang, B.X. Gu, Y.W. Gu, Simplified synthesis of single-
21
22 crystalline magnetic CoFe₂O₄ nanorods by a surfactant-assisted hydrothermal process, *J. Cryst. Growth.*
23
24 270 (2004) 156-161. DOI:10.1016/j.jcrysgr.2004.06.025
25
26 [40] S.K. Pradhan, S. Bidb, M. Gateshki, V. Petkov, Microstructure characterization and cation
27
28 distribution of nanocrystalline magnesium ferrite prepared by ball milling, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 93 (2005)
29
30 224-230.
31
32 [41] Y.M. Abbas, S.A. Mansour, M.H. Ibrahim, S.E. Ali, Microstructure characterization and cation
33
34 distribution of nanocrystalline cobalt ferrite, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 323 (2011) 2748-2756.
35
36 [42] D.J. Dunlop, Hysteresis properties of magnetite and their dependence on particle size: a test of
37
38 pseudo-single-domain remanence models, *J. Geophys. Res.* 91 (1986) 9569-9584. DOI:
39
40 10.1029/JB091iB09p09569
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
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